

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS AND DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT OF CRITICAL THINKING

Kh.A. Darvishkhodjaev

Lecturer, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, University of Business and Science

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Abstract. *This article discusses the scientific and theoretical foundations, methodological approaches, and practical significance of the concept of critical thinking. It also analyzes the formation of critical thinking and its relationship with psychological, pedagogical, and social factors.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, methodology, logical analysis, problem solving, reflection, independent thinking, creative approach.*

INTRODUCTION.

In modern society, the growth of knowledge, the speed of information flow, complex life situations require deep, reasoned and critical thinking from a person. Critical thinking is an active, independent and analytical form of human thinking that allows you to analyze, justify and evaluate any information [1].

It is important to highlight that the problem of training qualified personnel with comprehensive professional qualifications and the ability to think outside the box through the consistent introduction of the most effective teaching methods into educational processes is becoming increasingly urgent throughout the world. In our country, as in all other areas, fundamental reforms are consistently implemented in the fields of science and education, in particular in the higher education system. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev No. PF-5847 "On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" draws attention to the problem of "... students' lack of critical thinking skills, independent search and analysis of information" [1]. This creates the need for a deep and systematic study of this problem from a scientific and pedagogical point of view.

MAIN PART.

In modern educational processes, scientists from all over the world pay attention to the issues of "critical thinking" and offer various technologies and methods for its development, and this issue is being revised based on modern knowledge in philosophy, logic, pedagogy and psychology.

In the disciplines of pedagogy and psychology, foreign scientists P. Balonsky, V. Bolotov, T. Vorapai, A. Ivanova, A. Kocherga, V. Kushner, T. Oleynik, E. Polat, A. Podjelun, S. Romanova, M. Skatkin, I. Slobodanyuk, V. Teplov, L. Terletsкая, S. Terno, A. Tumantseva, Diana Galperi, A. Khachumyan, Jenny Steele, Kurt Meredith, Charles Temple approached this issue from the position of cognitive education. Uzbek scientists - E. Gaziev, A. Abdukodirov, R. Juraev, U. Inoyatov, O. K. Karshiev, H. Ibraimov, Sh. Abdullaeva, F. Khodjjeva, D. Roziyeva, D. Sharipova and others studied various aspects of the intellectual development of young people. However, although each researcher expressed their views, there is still no single, unified definition of the term "critical thinking". For example, L. Terletsкая argues that "critical thinking is the ability to

penetrate the essence of things, maintain consistency, adhering to critical rules, ask questions, find new approaches to explanation, be flexible in changing methods of solving a problem, quickly solve a problem" [2, - pp. 185-196]. T. Khauchman defines this phenomenon as "one of the main manifestations of mental activity, a strategy for finding the right way to solve any problem, which includes hypotheses, analysis (information processing, analytical verification, control, evaluation), reflexive influences, critical thinking - this is the ability to express one's own point of view, objectively evaluate the results of one's own and other people's activities, while embracing all the different opinions and views" [3, pp. 171–177].

In addition to this, it should be noted that V. Teplov, speaking about rational criticism, describes it as "a certain quality of human cognitive activity". Diana Halperi writes: "Critical thinking is a process that occurs simultaneously at several levels of active and interactive cognition. The owner of critical thinking is less susceptible to tricks, and since he has his own system of views, he is free from various dangers."

This also includes the idea that American scientists Jenny Steele, Kurt Meredith, Charles Templer in their views explain the psychological aspects of critical thinking as follows: "A person, being critical, gets acquainted with this or that idea, and also takes into account the possible consequences of their implementation. At the same time, a person initially perceives these ideas with a certain degree of mistrust and compares them with opposing points of view. To justify them, he uses a system of additional reasoning and on this basis develops his own point of view."

One of the preliminary considerations, Uzbek psychologist E. Gaziev states that "Critical thinking is the ability to check one's own and others' opinions, the truth or falsity of these opinions, as well as the ability to evaluate problematic situations."

In addition to the established theoretical frameworks, Uzbek scientist Sh. A. Abdullaeva writes that "Critical thinking is a form of thinking in which all mental operations (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction) are involved." Thus, in order to master the presented educational material, the student goes through the inductive (thinking with the purpose of generalizing individual, private experience and drawing conclusions) and deductive (ascending from the general to the particular) stages of cognitive processes. When they say "critical thinking", many focus on the negative meaning of its content and emphasize the inconsistency, which is considered the opposite of expediency. In fact, the English word "Critical" has a very deep meaning, does not deny relevance, but even has the same meaning as the word "Literacy", and when translated literally is considered a recognition used in relation to people who not only know how to read and write, but are also "literate and knowledgeable".

To be more specific the methodological foundations of the concept of "critical thinking" cannot be fully defined or expressed through several explanations or conclusions associated with it. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account that it has a broad and complex structure, objective and subjective nature. Our scientific and pedagogical research shows that "critical thinking" is inextricably linked and dialectically united with the following aspects:

- critical thinking, which embodies the ability to think and reason independently, without logical errors, to see the strengths and weaknesses of different opinions, and to evaluate them correctly;

- critical thinking - involves the activity of evaluating the correctness of events, thoughts, arguments and relationships, making informed choices, formulating appropriate questions for argumentation and finding new solutions and criteria for analysis through thinking based on the

ability to distinguish between arguments and opinions, identify evidence to support assumptions and establish logical connections between them;

- critical thinking is rational, reflective thinking, a factor that shows what to believe or what actions to take;

- critical thinking is the ability to see inconsistencies between the opinions expressed by a person or his behavior and generally accepted norms about him and his own ideas, perceptions, the ability to understand the truth or falsity of a theory, analyze and refute certain ideas, respond to them by proving them and directing them;

- critical thinking is a skill;

- the ability to make the right decisions, to see the difficulties that arise in the real world, to look for ways to solve them rationally using modern technologies, to critically analyze the acquired knowledge and apply it to solve new problems, to clearly know where and how the acquired knowledge can be applied in reality, etc. At the same time, critical thinking has the following very important characteristics:

- determines the features of the analytical selection and comparison of facts and phenomena;

- associativity, that is, ensuring the connection of previously established facts with events;

- logicity - the ability to build a sequence of actions, the logic of evidence when solving a problem;

- systematicity - the ability to consider an object and the problems in it from the point of view of their connections, the integrity of their properties, etc.

This can be understood as our opinion, critical thinking is a characteristic feature of a person, which includes the ability to understand the need to express one's position, not to act without proper analysis and comprehension of thoughts. This ability is directly related to the process of creative thinking. Although critical and creative thinking have their own characteristics, they interact and enter into feedback in the process of holistic and spontaneous thinking. Because their dialectical unity represents highly complex thinking. The concept of rationality is associated with critical thinking as an organizing principle, implying the optimal combination of goals and means. Creative thinking exists in the sphere of human relations and behavior. It is impossible to resolve moral, national, family, interpersonal conflicts through rationality. The upbringing and development of an intelligent person is aimed at practice, ordinary life logic, everyday speech, the use of multiple criteria.

According to A. Kocherga, human critical thinking combines the relationship of feelings and imagination. The main direction of the intellectual source of the idea of a critical attitude of a person is philosophy and general psychology, which leads to the emergence of external influences on mental, spiritual states in the following sequence: that is, inclination - ability - mechanism, and the psychological aspect of this is transferred to cognitive activity through the mechanism of reflection - design - reasoning.

Based on the above points, we can say that - "Critical thinking is "the process of a person's response to external information based on the knowledge he has and making decisions about what can be accepted, what needs to be supplemented or what should be rejected." At times, a person can change his personal views (beliefs, principles, worldviews, positions) or abandon them if the new information he receives turns out to be contradictory. Critical thinking teaches how to make changes in order to actively interact and coordinate with the new information he receives. Therefore, a person must not only trust his/her inner ability to think (think), but also have the

ability to find the most effective acceptable point in the conflict of different opinions, interacting, discussing and debating the opinions of other people. However, the process does not end there: we must implement critical thinking. When we increase our knowledge, not only our intellect is activated, but our feelings and sensations also change. Therefore, critical thinking is a product of social consciousness both in terms of its origin, in terms of its mode of activity, and in terms of its results.

For instance, in the field of education the main features of critical thinking include analysis (dividing the whole into structural parts) and synthesis (combining parts into a whole), abstraction (deriving the properties and connections of things from the mind), the processes of identifying specific problems and finding ways to solve them, putting forward hypotheses and ideas, the result of which is transformed into thought and explained (materialized) through speech. Therefore, critical thinking is a cognitive process aimed at understanding the most general, periodic, recurring patterns in internal connections when existing knowledge and experience collide with new knowledge (or information) in people, and can be logically refuted, it is a creative activity that can complement and harmonize, achieving perfection.

Critical thinking is a logical, reasoned, objective and systematic way of thinking. Its methodological foundations are formed on the basis of such disciplines as philosophy, logic, psychology and pedagogy:

- Philosophical basis - the ideas of doubt, evaluation of alternative opinions, relativity of knowledge go back to the views of Descartes, Kant and other philosophers.

- Psychological basis - critical thinking is formed through the processes of human perception, perception and processing of knowledge.

- Pedagogical basis - includes methods for developing critical thinking in students through problem solving activities [4].

- Critical thinking has several important features, in contrast to simple thinking:

- Proof - opinions and conclusions are based on specific evidence.

- Analytical - dividing information into parts and evaluating each part.

- Objectivity - thinking without personal emotions and views.

- Reflections - observation, analysis and evaluation of one's own mental activity.

- Ability to see alternative solutions - the ability to evaluate any problem from different angles [5].

Critical thinking is formed under the influence of the following factors:

- Active methods in the educational process - problem situations, debates, cases.

- Family and social environment - an environment where there is an open exchange of ideas and the possibility of independent decision-making.

- Personal characteristics - intellectual curiosity, openness, the ability to doubt [6].

It must be emphasized that critical thinking is one of the important competencies in modern professions and life situations. It protects a person from stereotypical thinking, helps to make non-standard decisions, serves to resist manipulation [7].

CONCLUSION

The above analysis allows us to conclude that since critical thinking is extremely complex and at the same time very important in a person's life, the formation of such thinking in our youth is important in the preparation of potential personnel who are able to look at reality with their own eyes, have their own clear position and a reliable trajectory of action. Our current task as teachers

is to develop and implement in practice a clear scientific and methodological concept for the development of such thinking in students based on modern pedagogical approaches.

To summarize the main point critical thinking is a necessary intellectual skill for a modern person, the formation and development of which requires methodologically sound approaches. It helps a person to become independent, conscious and socially active.

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